

Lingual Expressions of Power Forms in Writing Classes

(Case Study on the Students in 5th Semester)

E. Worobroto P.
Universitas Brawijaya
Malang, Indonesia

Masilva Raynox Mael
Universitas Negeri Surabaya
Surabaya, Indonesia

Ismi Prihandari
Universitas Brawijaya
Malang, Indonesia

Parastuti
Universitas Negeri Surabaya
Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:- This research aims to describe the forms of power in directive speech acts through hegemony representations in the *Sakubun* (Writing) Class of 5th-semester students. This research uses a qualitative approach. Data analysis techniques are done by recording the class activities; the interaction between the lecturer and students. The next step is documenting the collected data, and taking notes of the data. Data validation is using an intense discussion with colleagues, in addition, to figuring a triangulation used on data sources and triangulation between researchers.

The results of this research are expected to show forms of power discourse related to the interaction of lecturers and students in the teaching and learning process in the *Sakubun* 5 class.

Keywords:- Representation of Power, Forms of Power, Writing, Writing Class.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research is concerned with the problem of discourse. Discourse is the use of language in communication events or a social situation (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2004, p.34). The use of language in communication is always associated with the use of language to fulfill its function. The function of language can be understood as how a person uses a language or several languages to achieve his communication goals. As a communication event, discourse relates to all events or events that can be identified. As a product produced by communication events, discourse is a series of lingual units that are not only loaded with meaning but as grammatical units that contain messages. Discourse is a unit of behavior realized by lingual units. As a unit of behavior, discourse is a form or image as well as an expression and representation of the phenomena of human life.

This study examines the representation of forms of power in directive speech acts between the lecturers of the *Sakubun* 5 course and the students participating in the lecture. Directive speech acts are performed when the speaker wants the interlocutor to do something according to what he said. This speech act is used by the speaker to order the interlocutor to do something. According to Yule (2006:93), directive speech acts

include orders, suggestions, invitations, requests, messages, and requests. The representation of power is studied using discourse analysis to see how the form of power of the course instructor is manifested in the language, through text discourse in the form of conversations between lecturers and students during lectures.

II. METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach. The decision to use a qualitative approach is based on linguistic practices that appear either explicitly or implicitly in the learning process in the classroom. The linguistic practices are the source of this research data. The analysis was carried out descriptively and data validation using triangulation and peer checking. The qualitative approach here focuses on disclosing the power that is represented in the conversation between lecturers and students in the writing class.

In this study, the unit of research analysis is in the form of diction, expressions, and sentences in conversations that contain elements of the hegemony of power. Therefore, this study seeks to reveal the representation of the hegemony of power contained in the text in the form of words, phrases, and sentences, which occur in the communication between lecturers and students.

The research data is a textual discourse which is the main source of lecturer and student conversations during the learning process. This was done with the hope that the data collected would be in the form of descriptions of speech models representing hegemony focused on forms of power. The research analysis uses discourse analysis. This method is used because the expected data findings are the text.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of classroom learning, the teacher often uses direct and indirect commands. The use of the two forms of commands is also influenced by the components of speech, especially the topic of speech and the purpose of the speech. When the teacher discusses objective topics of speech and emphasizes understanding the substance of learning (transactional learning substance), the teacher tends to use direct command. Direct command is considered to be able to

bridge the achievement of the objectives of these topics. This can be seen in the sentences from the following data.:

1) S: 先生、おはようございます。

Good morning Sensei.

作文 6-B クラスの マリスカです。G C で共有されたクイズのリンクについて、質問したいです。

I'm Mariska Ellysabeth from Sakubun 6-B class. I want to ask, about the quiz link shared on Google Classroom.

T: おはよう。

Good morning,

今すぐクイズの質問に教えてください。09.00 からやってください。

Answer the quiz questions right now. Starting at 09.00

S: 分かりました。友だちに伝えます。

All right, I'll pass it on to my friends, thank you.

(Data 3)

However, when conveying subjective learning substances that emphasize personal or social (interactional) relationships, teachers tend to use a lot of indirect commands. These symptoms are revealed in the following two quotes.

2) S: 先生、おはようございます。

Good morning Sensei.

今日の勉強については何かクラスのメンバーに報告したい事がありますか。

for today's class is there any information that I need to convey to my friends, Sensei?

T: ちょっと待って、このリンクを使用して、授業を参照してください。

Wait a minute, **please join using this link.**

S: 分かりました。友だちに伝えます。

All right, I'll pass it on to my friends, thank you.

(Data 1)

3) S: 先生、質問です。断食の間、作文クラスは何時にはじまりますか。

Sensei, I want to ask again, during the fasting month what time does the Sakubun V-B class start?

T: 以前のように 9 時から。

as before at 09.00

(Data 9)

In the three quotations above it appears that the teacher uses direct and indirect commands. The use of the two forms of command is aligned with the topic of speech being discussed in the learning process. In quotations 2) and 3) as seen in data 1 and 9, the teacher uses indirect commands to convey speech topics related to personal or social relationships, in this case, the teacher uses declarative sentences containing notifications. The notification is presented implicitly so that the illocutionary power of the command must be interpreted from the indirect command in quotations 2) and 3). Meanwhile, in quote 1), the teacher uses direct command for students to work on quiz questions which will be held at 09:00. The intent of the command is explicitly captured from the utterances that build the command.

The quotations contain sentences in the form of direct commands and indirect commands used by the teacher above, aiming to give directions to students at the beginning of the semester. By its role, the teacher has the legal power to provide direction and learning programs at the beginning of the semester.

When compared to imperative sentences, request sentences have a lower level of restriction so that the power represented tends to be more humane. The results of this study it was revealed that all speech participants in class discourse could use requests. Therefore, in the learning process, if the context allows, teachers or students have the same legitimacy to use request sentences. Look at the following quote.

4) S: The link still doesn't work. **Please tell other friends to just read RPS and jugyo nagare on Google Classroom.** The PDF material is also available on Google Classroom.

M: All right Sensei. So for a while, there's no class today, right Sensei? Then I'm allowed to ask, for the absence, do we do the absence via SIAM, Sensei?

(Data 2)

5) G: Good afternoon Sensei, sorry to interrupt. I, Mariska Ellysabeth, would like to inform you that in the class of 2019, only Indri Novianti, passed N2. Thank You

S: **Fine. Can Indri contact Sensei?** Thank you. (Data 6)

From quotations 4) and 5) it is revealed that the directive acts with the form of a request, namely the use of the modality please in 4), and the use of the form of a question to ask in 5). The use of these adverb modalities seems to reduce the level of power restriction represented. Without the presence of these modalities, the speech of the request becomes a form of direct command with an imperative structure that tends to represent more dominating power. Likewise with the interrogative form in 5). In this context, the teacher uses an interrogative structured request 5) to ask students to convey their message to the student in question. The interrogative request utterance will become imperative if it uses a declarative form.

Both requests represent the legitimate power of the teacher. In his capacity as a teacher, the teacher has the

legitimate power to ask students to answer questions. The power represented by the request is very humane. In that context, there is no visible attempt by the teacher to dominate the students, but there is a teacher effort to reduce the level of the request restriction.

The results of further research show that teachers, as deontic sources, are speech participants who use more prohibitions than students. The use of the prohibition can occur in the process of giving directions or in the learning process. The following quote is an example of a prohibition used by teachers.

6) G: Good afternoon sensei. Sorry to disturb your time. My name is Mariska, please allow me to state the reason for the absence of my friends from class V-B Sakubun:

1. Amina: Last Wednesday she took part in a competition in Social Sciences and sent permission to Sensei's WA, but it couldn't be sent. Meanwhile, today he was excused from taking classes due to a cold. 2. Sherwin: not feeling well. 3. Rayhan: there was a power outage. This is Amina's last Wednesday dispensation letter. That's all, thank you, Sensei.

S: Hmm... You need a doctor's note for being sick, if not, you are in absent status.

G: all right Sensei, I'll pass it on to the friends concerned. Thanks for the information, Sensei. (Data 4)

7) G: I am sorry before, Sensei, I want to ask, here are some of my friends whose hours crashed with Bunpo class, what should I do, Sensei?

S: stay in class, and join the class until 10.25. (Data 11)

The power represented by the prohibition in quote 6) above is more humane than the prohibition in quote 7). The indirectness of the prohibition structure reduces the level of restriction that is generated so that it tends to represent a more humanist power. Prohibitions 6) and 7) both have a declarative structure, but prohibition 7) has a stronger signal structure. Both of them have a lower level of restriction than a direct ban. The formal structure of the two utterances does not indicate a prohibition. However, the implicature of the speech shows a prohibition so that students do not play truant, especially with reasons that seem far-fetched.

The use of prohibitions above tends to represent reference power or behavioral power. According to the teacher, the use of such a form of prohibition can reduce the threat of face. Despite its indirect nature, in certain contexts, the use of such prohibitions is very effective. This proves the truth of Froyen's opinion (1993:57) which states that in class discourse, there are three prominent powers, namely expert/expertise power, legitimate power, and reference power.

IV. CONCLUSION

Regarding the representation of power in directive acts, the speech participants in class discourse use three types of directive acts, namely orders, requests, and prohibitions. The use of directive acts of the type of commands and prohibitions has a high degree of restriction and tends to represent dominative power. However, the orders and prohibitions found in the research data are pronounced indirectly by using directive sentence forms so that the level of restriction is lower and feels more humane. Meanwhile, the use of requests clearly shows a low level of restriction so it is also clear in representing humanist power. The degree of restriction and the nature of the power affect the legitimacy of the user of the directive. By its institutional role, the teacher has the legitimacy to command and prohibit students, but not vice versa. The forms of power that emerge from directive actions in the Sakubun class are valid, expert, and reference/behavior forms of power.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Brown, Gillian dan George Yu,le, "Analisis Wacana". Jakarta: Gramdia Pustak Utama, 1996.
- [2]. Halliday, M.A.K & Matthiessen, "An Introduction to Functional Grammar", third edition, Great Britain: Hodder Education, 2004.
- [3]. Hughes, R. L., Ginnet, R. C., dan Curphy, G. J., "Leadership: Enhancing the Lessons of Experience", 6th Edition, McGraw-Hill International Edition, Singapore, 2009.
- [4]. Jones, Steve, "Antonio Gramsci", New York: Routledge, 2006.
- [5]. Saussure, Ferdinand, "Cours de Linguistique Generale (Pengantar Linguistik Umum)", Dialih bahasakan Rahayu S. Hidayat, Yogyakarta: Gajahmada University Pers, 1993.
- [6]. Wareing, Shân & Thomas, Linda, "Language, Society and Power: An Introduction", London ; New York : Routledge, 2007.